

USING OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE INTERVENTIONS IN CHOLELITHIASIS

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Increasing the frequency of gallstone disease with choledocholithiasis and stricture distal choledoch a growing number of surgical interventions, including the use of new technologies. At the present level of development surgery, there are two basic ways endosurgical the treatment of this disease two-stage, comprising endoscopic papillo sphincterotomy before or after laparoscopic cholecystectomy and laparoscopic stage in volume cholecystectomy in combination with interference on a common gall duct.

Purpose of the study. To determine the effectiveness of laparoscopic surgery in the treatment of choledocholithiasis and stenosis of the distal common bile duct, with no possibility of endoscopic interventions on a large papilla duodenal intestine.

Materials and methods. Analyzed 47 patients who performed laparoscopic cholecystectomy during the period from September to December 2021 in department of surgery in the Fergana branch of Republican Research Centre Of Emergency Medicine.

Results. Laparoscopic methods of treatment of cholelithiasis, complicated choledocholithiasis and distal stenosis of choledoch are the methods of choice, along with convention al treatments. Positive results have been reported in at 90.7% of the patients, the compli cation rate is 10.6% and the mortality rate of 0%. In conventional methods, these figures are 17.4% and 3.19%. Time spent in hospital is reduced from 14,9 to 8,8 days. Laparoscopic choledoholitotomy it is indicated for single calculi and good paten cy the distal common bile duct and is effective in 92.8% of cases. Choledochoduodenostomy carried out in violation of patency distal part of the common bile duct, plural choledocholithiasis and increase in the more than 1.5 cm. Formation choledochoduodenoanastomosis, as well as choledoholitotomy, must be combined with an external drainage common bile duct through the cystic stump duct.

Conclusions. Laparoscopic choledoholitotomy and choledochoduodenostomy is an effective treatment. These interventions are accompanied by fewer complications compared with conventional surgery operations.